

RULE OF LAW INDEX, 2020: AN ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF INDIA'S RULE OF LAW MECHANISM

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of Rule of Law is as old as the writings of Plato and Aristotle. Plato once wrote “Where the law is subject to some other authority and has none of its own, the collapse of the state, in my view, is not far off; but if law is the master of the government and the government is its slave, then the situation is full of promise and men enjoy all the blessings that the gods shower on a state”¹. Similarly, Aristotle was of the view that “law should govern and those who are in power should be servants of the laws”.²

The term Rule of Law is derived from the French term “*la principe de legalite*” which literally means the principles of legality and a system or a government that runs on the principles of law and not on the principles of certain individuals. It is a state of affairs in which there are legal barriers to governmental arbitrariness and there are available legal safeguards for the protection of the individuals.³

Sir Edward Coke, the Chief Justice in James I's reign is said to be the originator of the concept. In his banter against James I's reign, Sir Coke succeeded in maintaining that the king must be under the God. It was A.V. Dicey who developed this doctrine in his famous work “Law and the Constitution” (1865).

According to A.V. Dicey, rule of law refers to the following three aspects:

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¹ Plato and Aristotle on Tyranny and Rule of Law, *available at*: <https://www.crf-usa.org/bill-of-rights-in-action/bria-26-1-plato-and-aristotle-on-tyranny-and-the-rule-of-law.html>; (Last Visited on February 15, 2021).

² Introduction to the concept of Rule of Law, *available at*: <https://www.lawteacher.net/free-law-essays/constitutional-law/introduction-concept-of-rule-law%20essays.php#ftn1>; (Last Visited on February 15, 2021).

³ Rule of Law, *available at*: http://ijlls.in/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/Rule_of_Law.pdf, (Last visited on February 15, 2021).

Figure 1: Aspects of Rule of Law by Dicey

These three foundations of rule of law have been followed diligently as a pedantic and theoretical concept. The concept has been accepted at the international level as the modern form of law of nature by the Delhi Declaration of International Commission of Jurists, 1958 which was affirmed in Lagos in 1961.

Many legal systems such as the English legal system has adopted Rule of Law within their justice delivery mechanism as evident from *Entick v. Carrington*⁴ and *Wilkes v. Wood*.⁵

On the similar lines, the concept of Rule of Law has been incorporated within the Indian legal system through several constitutional provisions and judicial pronouncements.

However, mere adoption of a principle does not guarantee its effective implementation. There needs to be a barometer which tests this implementation. The Rule of Law Index by the World Justice Project is such an initiative which gauges Rule of Law in various nations. Although, the Index does not find its place in the common discussions in relation to law and administration, its findings can highlight the legal and the administrative environment of a nation.

⁴ (1765) 19 St Tr 1029: 95 ER 807.

⁵ (1763) 19 St Tr 1153: 98 ER 489.

RULE OF LAW IN INDIA

Rule of law in India has progressed into multiple dimensions and has transcended beyond the tri-modelled principle postulated by A.V. Dicey. Rule of Law in India is based upon constitutional principles and administrative actions. It is metaphorical vehicle of which Constitution is the fuel and administrative actions are the functionary tyres. The Constitution validates it, the administrative actions give motion to the same.

Rule of Law is *sine qua non* for any democracy. The sentiment was proclaimed by the Supreme Court in *Bachan Singh v. State of Punjab*⁶ whereby Bhagwati J. stated that Rule of Law is a concept that “permeates” the entire fabric of the Constitution. The Court declared its as one of the ‘basic features’ of the Constitution.

Similarly, in *A.K. Kripaik v. Union of India*⁷, the Supreme Court stated that law was supreme over all the fields of administration in India.

The concept of rule of law exists in the nation by virtue of the following features:

1. Supremacy of Law:

This aspect of rule of law finds its place within the Constitution of India. The ideals of Justice, Liberty and Equality adopted in the Preamble of the Constitution reflect the principle of Rule of Law in India.

Judicial pronouncements have also validated on this aspect of rule of law in India. As held in *A.K. Gopalan v. State of Madras*⁸ that the Constitution is supreme (para 145). All the three organs of the State are under the Constitution and act according to the provisions of the Constitution.

Furthermore, any malice within the working of the executive or the government is a violation of Rule of Law as held in *Express Newspaper (P) Ltd. v. Union of India*.⁹

The executive and legislative powers of the State and the Union are required to be exercised according to the provisions of the Constitution. Also, if the government and public officials encroach upon the fundamental rights of the people, they can be regulated by the use of writs by the Courts.

2. Equality Before Law:

⁶ AIR (1982) SC 1336.

⁷ AIR (1970) SC 150.

⁸ AIR (1950) SC 27.

⁹ (1986) 1 SCC 133.

Article-14 of the Constitution enshrines this aspect. Further, The aspect “Equality Before Law” is a direct emulation of rule of law doctrine.

Everyone is equal before law and the “king can do no wrong” has no application within India. The Supreme Court even emphasised on this in *Indira Nehru Gandhi v. Raj Narain*¹⁰ whereby the Court held that the rule of law is embodied in Article 14 of the Constitution of India and is part of the basic structure of the Constitution and it cannot be demolished even by an Amendment under Article 368.

3. *Predominance of Legal Spirit:*

The Rights in the Constitution of India has been guaranteed to every person and is enforceable by the Courts under various writs. This principle of Predominance of Legal Spirit was used in interpretation of Constitutional provisions in several cases such as *A.K. Gopalan v. State of Madras*¹¹ and *Ram Prasad v. State*.¹²

This aspect can be validated by referring to *Chief Settlement Commissioner, Punjab v. Om Prakash*¹³ whereby the Court held that the rule of law also includes the power of the courts to “test all administrative actions”.

Social Welfare

Social Welfare is also an aspect of Rule of Law. In the case of *Veena Sethi v. State of Bihar*¹⁴ whereby the question of illegal detention of certain prisoners for two to three decades was in issue. The Court held that Rule of Law does not extend only to those who can fight for their rights, but also to poor and down-trodden.

In *People’s Union for Democratic Rights v. Union of India*¹⁵, popularly known as “Asiad Case”, the Supreme Court held that rule of law does not mean that it must be available to only a fortunate few. The poor too have civil and political rights and rule of law is also meant for them.

¹⁰ AIR (1975) SC 2299.

¹¹ *Supra* note 8.

¹² AIR (1953) SC 215.

¹³ AIR (1969) SC 33.

¹⁴ AIR (1983) SC 339.

¹⁵ AIR (1982) SC 1473.

RULE OF LAW INDEX

The World Justice Project (WJP) Rule of Law Index 2020 is an annual report that gauged the countries on the basis of Rule of Law from the perspective of citizens as well as academicians.

The World Justice Project is an “independent, multidisciplinary organisation” that works for the vociferous spread of the rule of law mechanism all over the world. The Organisation was established in 2006 by William H. Neucum in a collaborative initiative of the American Bar Association.

The WJP Rule of Law Index 2020 portrays rule of law mechanism in 128 countries by providing scores and rankings based on eight factors, which are

1. Constraints on Government Powers
2. Absence of Corruption
3. Open Government
4. Fundamental Rights
5. Order and Security
6. Regulatory Enforcement
7. Civil Justice
8. Criminal Justice

The current set of Index is a result of surveys whereby 130,000 Household Surveys and 4,000 Expert Surveys were conducted in the 128 participating countries.¹⁶ The Index is based on primary data which has been collected in lines with the opinions of the citizens regarding the status of rule of law in their respective nations.

The Index has been created so that it reflects the picture of the administrative and judicial system of the respective nations not just to the people at the helm of the affairs but to the citizens as a whole.

The 2020 Index was topped by Denmark, Norway and Finland. While Venezuela, Cambodia and Democratic Republic of Congo fared at the bottom of the Index.

¹⁶ WJP Rule of Law Index 2020, available at: <https://worldjusticeproject.org/our-work/research-and-data/wjp-rule-law-index-2020> (Visited On February 16, 2020).

Mode of Data Collection

The scores and rankings of the eight factors and 44 sub-factors of the Index draw from two sources of data collected by the WJP¹⁷:

1. A General Population Poll (GPP) conducted by leading local polling companies, using a representative sample of 1,000 respondents in each country
2. Qualified Respondents' Questionnaires (QRQs) consisting of closed-ended questions completed by in-country practitioners and academics with expertise in civil and commercial law, criminal justice, labour law, and public health.

Basis of Formulating the Index

The report has been framed on the basis of four universal principles of Rule of Law. These Principles are mentioned in the rule of law report as follows:

1. **Accountability:**
This means that both the sectors of the state that is public and private are responsible. Meaning thereby, that the government as well as private actors are accountable under the law.
2. **Just Laws:**
The laws are clearly stated and free from any bias. Further, such laws must protect the fundamental rights as well as the human rights.
3. **Open Government:**
The government must be transparent in framing of law, enacting it and its application. Further, such application must be fair & efficient.
4. **Accessible and Impartial Dispute Resolution:**
The administration of justice must be free from any bias and must be delivered by the competent authority without compromising on the ethical facets.

Furthermore, according to the Rule of Law Index, 2020 these indicators are linked to two chief principles that refer to the relationship between the state. One, regarding the limits imposed by the law on the State in exercise of its power on the citizens and the other, the limits imposed by the States on the society.

¹⁷ World Justice Project, Report: *World Justice Project Rule of Law Index 2020*.

FRAMEWORK OF RULE OF LAW INDEX INDICATORS

The Rule of Law Index works on the aforementioned several indicators. However, there are various factors that determine these indicators in itself. These indicators are evaluated on the basis of following components:

	FACTORS	COMPONENTS
	<p><i>CONSTRAINTS ON GOVERNMENT POWERS</i></p>	<p>Government powers are effectively limited by the legislature.</p> <p>Government powers are effectively limited by the judiciary.</p> <p>Government powers are effectively limited by independent auditing and review.</p> <p>Government officials are sanctioned for misconduct.</p> <p>Government powers are subject to non-governmental checks.</p> <p>Transition of power is subject to the law.</p>
	<p><i>ABSENCE OF CORRUPTION</i></p>	<p>Government officials in the executive branch do not use public office for private gain.</p> <p>Government officials in the judicial branch do not use public office for private gain.</p> <p>Government officials in the police & the military do not use public office for private gain.</p> <p>Government officials in the legislative branch do not use public office for private gain.</p>

	<i>OPEN GOVERNMENT</i>	<p>Publicized laws & government data.</p> <p>Right to information.</p> <p>Civic participation.</p> <p>Complaint mechanisms.</p>
	<i>FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS</i>	<p>Equal treatment & absence of discrimination.</p> <p>The right to life & security of the person is effectively guaranteed.</p> <p>Due process of the law and rights of the accused.</p> <p>Freedom of opinion & expression is effectively guaranteed.</p> <p>Freedom of belief & religion is effectively guaranteed.</p> <p>Freedom from arbitrary interference with privacy is effectively guaranteed.</p> <p>Freedom of assembly & association is effectively guaranteed.</p> <p>Fundamental labour rights are effectively guaranteed.</p>
	<i>ORDER AND SECURITY</i>	<p>Crime is effectively controlled.</p> <p>Civil conflict is effectively limited.</p> <p>People do not resort to violence to redress personal grievances.</p>
	<i>REGULATORY ENFORCEMENT</i>	<p>Government regulations are effectively enforced.</p> <p>Government regulations are applied & enforced without improper influence.</p> <p>Administrative proceedings are conducted without unreasonable delay.</p> <p>Due process is respected in administrative proceedings.</p> <p>The government does not expropriate</p>

		without lawful process & adequate compensation.
	<i>CIVIL JUSTICE</i>	<p>People can access & afford civil justice.</p> <p>Civil justice is free of discrimination.</p> <p>Civil justice is free of corruption.</p> <p>Civil justice is free of improper government influence.</p> <p>Civil justice is not subject to unreasonable delay.</p> <p>Civil justice is effectively enforced.</p> <p>Alternative dispute resolution mechanisms are accessible, impartial, and effective.</p>
	<i>CRIMINAL JUSTICE</i>	<p>Criminal investigation system is effective</p> <p>Criminal adjudication system is timely and effective</p> <p>Correctional system is effective in reducing criminal behaviour</p> <p>Criminal justice system is impartial</p> <p>Criminal justice system is free of corruption</p> <p>Criminal justice system is free of improper government influence</p> <p>Due process of the law & rights of the accused</p>

Table 1: Factors and the Respective Components of The WJP Rule of Law Index

The above table describes as to how extensive the coverage of rule of law is in practice. While many scholars and theorists often surmise Rule of Law into the tri-principled doctrine of Dicey, its actual coverage is much wider and more extensive. Its ambit starts from the

powers of the government and spans across transparency, rights, security, regulation and dispensing of various forms of justice.

Informal Justice

Rule of Law Index mentions an additional factor to the estimation of rule of law across the world, that is, *Informal Justice*. This refers to the justice delivery outside the formal civil and criminal justice lines. The WJP collects data on the informal justice through various surveys. However, measurement of this kind of indicator is difficult due to the complexities of this system and the non-uniformity attached to it.

INDIA'S PERFORMANCE IN THE RULE OF LAW INDEX 2020

India's performance in the Rule of Law Index, 2020 can be categorised as average. Globally, it ranked 69th out of 128 nations. India saw a one rank slump in comparison to the Rule of Law Index, 2019 and Four rank drop from the Index of 2018, with an overall score of 0.51 points.

However, amongst its South Asian counterparts, India ranked 3rd out of the six nations of the region after Nepal and Sri Lanka, whose overall rank were 61 and 66, respectively. A detailed analysis of India's performance across various parameters is as under:

A. Constraints on Government Power

In this aspect of Rule of Law, India scored a factor score of 0.61 out of 1 which was highest in the South Asian Region and 41st on a global level. The reason for this can be attributed to the fact that India has a robust mechanism of law and the judiciary. There are several checks on government power through various mechanisms such as judicial review. Furthermore, the other nations of the South Asian Regions are usually involved in political turmoil and hence, there often exists a proxy government backed by the rebel groups or by the Army such as Pakistan and Myanmar, respectively.

B. Absence of Corruption

In this aspect, India scored a factor score of 0.42 (a drop of 0.01 from preceding year) which was second highest in the South Asian region and 85th globally. The global rank in this aspect

can be said to be below average, to say the least. The reasons attributed to the same is the ground level corruption and absence of a vigilance body over the organs of the government.

Though India appointed a Lokpal in Justice Pinaki Ghosh, but the efficiency and effectiveness of the Lokpal Act, 2013 has no correlation with his appointment. Furthermore, vigilance agencies such as Enforcement Directorate and the Central Bureau of Investigation in India are often maligned to be working at the behest of the government in power, which not only puts the anti-corruption mechanism into question but also casts serious doubts regarding the willingness of the democratic nation to counter it.

C. Open Government

In the facet of open government, India scores on the same lines as it did in constraints on government power that is, 0.61. Its regionally ranked first and globally ranks in this aspect is 32nd out of 128 nations (a jump of two places from the Index of 2019).

This is a significant aspect of rule of law status in India which can be attributed to several legislations such as the Right to Information Act, 2005 and digitisation of major government services in the recent past. Also, with e-delivery of services being introduced in India, this facet has improved.

D. Fundamental Rights

This is the most vocal aspect of modern-day democracy. From Bill of Rights in the American Constitution to the Fundamental Rights within Part III of the Indian Constitution, this aspect is something very essential to the rule of law.

In the aspect of fundamental rights, India's factor score is just above average at 0.51 ranking third in the South Asian region and 84th globally (a drop of 9 ranks). However, this can be attributed to the several incidents such as infringement of privacy rights by the State, reports of restrictions on freedom of speech and expression as supported by a constant slump in India's rankings in the Press Freedom Index, 2020 to 142 from 140 in 2019.

E. Order and Security

The aspect of order and security is very much relevant to the modern-day States. With the impending doom in the form of terrorism and extremism, order and security is the worst hit. With order and security in shambles, the rule of law's position is consequently bleak.

India's score in this aspect was close to better at 0.59. However, it ranked 4th locally and 114th globally. The fact that it ranks behind some of the most volatile States speaks volume about the order and security situation in India. The reason for this can be stated to be several incidents of terrorism across the nation and several internal bursts of violence over certain issues in the past year.

F. Regulatory Enforcement

The enforcement of regulations is important in any civilised State. It is the regulations that keep the unhinged powers in check and ensures that there is no misuse of power by the administrative bodies.

India ranks 98th on a global scale in this aspect of Rule of Law, which is a massive drop of 12 ranks from Rule of Law Index, 2019. Its factor score is below average at 0.45. This low score can be correlated with the reasons attributed to low score in the absence of corruption aspect namely, bounding of enforcing agencies such as CBI and ED and also, delay in enforcement is also one of the causes of this low score.

G. Civil Justice

Justice is an important barometer for the efficiency of the rule of law mechanism of any nation. A State having efficient justice delivery mechanism can enforce rule of law and protect the rights of the individuals. The WJP evaluates justice on two fronts namely, Civil Justice and Criminal Justice.

India ranked 98th globally and second in the South Asian region in this factor of Rule of Law with factor score of 0.45. The score and the rank are both below average.

This is perhaps due to the truth in stereotype of a delayed justice delivery system in India. With 18.75 lakh civil cases pending in High Courts of India¹⁸ (as stated by the Law Minister of India), this low rank seems to be on somewhat correct lines.

H. Criminal Justice

This factor witnesses the lowest Factor Score across all the factors for India. With a below average factor score of 0.40 and a global rank of 78, this aspect throws a very significant

¹⁸ Out of 43 lakh cases pending in High Courts, over 8 lakh a decade old *available at*: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/out-of-43-lakh-cases-pending-in-high-courts-over-8-lakh-a-decade-old/articleshow/69974916.cms> (Last Modified June 27, 2019).

perspective at our faces. The criminal justice delivery mechanism in the nation is already associated with a bad repute with many cases not even getting reported due to lacunas at the fundamental level of law & order services.

Even those who get reported, are mostly subject to delayed administration of justice as evident by the statement given by the Indian Law Minister that a total of 12.15 lakh criminal cases are pending across various High Court of the nation.¹⁹

Hence, the report reflects to us the status of Rule of Law in India. In certain aspects India fares decently, while in some its performance lacks as against the expected standards. The problem does not lie with the concept in theory but with concept in practice. While Dicey's principle finds ground in judicial pronouncements and the law of the nation, its practice does not connote to these developments in real sense. Its score is again satisfactory, but if the reputation of being the world's largest democracy is to be attached beforehand in this score, calling it satisfactory would be an overstatement.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTIONS

Therefore, to sum up one can state that the situation of Rule of Law in India in theory is very sound. It lies on the foundations of Constitutional Provisions such as Article 13, Article-14, Article- 19 and Article-21 and on the judicial pronouncements of ADM Jabalpur v. Shivakant Shukla²⁰ and Indira Nehru Gandhi v. Raj Narain.²¹ Rule of Law, thus, is a sound principle in theory in the Indian context.

The application of Rule of Law is showcased by the Rule of Law Index, 2020. And if the application is to be gauged, it does not match up to the expectations associated with the Indian democracy.

However, not all is so loose in this fabric of rule of law. There are still certain positives that can be taken from this report such as its performance in open government and constraints on government powers. These aspects show that on the foundations of equality before law, the State is doing a lot better than the report gives it credit for in real sense. With the advent of several e-governance measures and public interest litigations along with judicial activism- these aspects are bound to get strengthened with the test of time.

¹⁹ *Supra* note 18.

²⁰ (1976) 2 SCC 521.

²¹ *Supra* note 10.

The other aspects need improvement in one way or the other. The problems addressed in the analysis of the reports are to be resolved first hand. For the resolution of these problems, there is the pre-requisite of intent and execution. Intent on the part of the Montesquieuan divisions of power and execution on the part of these divisions and the people themselves.

Any changes, to any aspect of any sector requires the plough of execution along with sowing of intent of execution. It is a participatory process in which every individual, whether belonging to the administration or to the administered has to play his/her part collectively rather than individually.

It is only through these two ends of periscope that the situation of the rule of law would rise above the existing ocean of despotism that is prevailing all over the world. The status at which newer democracies have already reached and India, being the mother of all democracies is still to touch the checkpoint. This all, would be possible by collective effort and systematic execution of rule of law mechanisms in the nation which already is seeing a slump not just in the rankings but in the effective implementation of the principle.

